

Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of novel 5-substituted pyrimidin-2,4,6-triones

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Abstract : 5-Benzylpyrimidin-2,4,6-triones (3a-c), 5-((furan-2-yl)methyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (3g) and 5-((3-aryl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-triones (3h-j) were obtained in two steps. Reaction of barbituric acid (1) with various substituted aromatic aldehydes, furfuraldehyde and 3-aryl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbaldehydes in methanol yielded the corresponding chalcones 2a-m in 48–85% yield. These chalcones on reduction with sodium borohydride in isopropyl alcohol furnished desired novel compounds 3a-c and 3g-j in 55–85% yield. The structure of all the synthesized compounds have been established by various spectral studies and elemental analysis. All the synthesized compounds have been screened for antimicrobial activity.

Keywords : Chalcones, 5-benzylpyrimidin-2,4,6-triones, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Barbiturates are a class of drugs derived from 2,4,6-(1H,3H,5H)-pyrimidinetriones are commonly called as barbituric acids¹. A large number of closely related barbiturates like phenobarbital, meberal, seconal, nembital, amytal and pentothal have been synthesized and found to be clinically useful antisedative and hypnotic drugs². Recently, barbituric acid derivatives found to be useful in cancer and AIDS therapy³, and also as matrix metalloprotease inhibitors⁴. Mallik *et al.* were recently synthesized barbiturate-based methionine aminopeptidase-I inhibitors⁵. Ray *et al.* were synthesized various barbituric acid analogs as a novel and non-steroidal glucocorticoid receptor modulators⁶. The pharmacological activity in barbiturates was observed due to the substitution at C₅-position of the pyrimidine nucleus⁷⁻⁹.

Substituted pyrazole ring also exhibits a broad spectrum of biological activities such as antidiabetic, antibacterial, antimicrobial and herbicidal. Pyrazole analogs have been known for their potent biological activities¹⁰⁻¹². In addition, pyrazole nucleus also exhibits pharmacological interest as antianxiety, antipyretic, analgesic and anti-inflammatory drugs. In particular, 4-functionalized 1,3-diphenylpyrazoles as antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antiparasitic and antidiabetic drugs¹³. Prakash *et al.* re-

cently synthesized substituted pyrazole derivatives as potent antifungal agents¹⁴. These findings in the literature prompted us to undertake the synthesis of pyrazole-4-carboxaldehyde derivatives.

In continuation of our research in the area of synthesis and development of modified pyrimidines and pyrazoles¹⁵⁻²¹ for various biological activities, we report here in the synthesis and antimicrobial activities of 5-benzylpyrimidin-2,4,6-triones (3a-c), 5-((furan-2-yl)methyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (3g) and 5-((3-aryl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-triones (3h-j).

Results and discussion

Reaction of barbituric acid (1) with various substituted aromatic aldehydes, furfuraldehyde and 3-aryl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carboxaldehydes²² in methanol at refluxing temperature for 4 h furnished the desired compounds (2a-m) in 48–85% yield. Formation of these compounds 2a-m were confirmed by various spectral data. The IR spectrum of compound 2a shows the presence of NH at 3210, 3069 and C=O at 1727 cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR spectrum shows singlet at δ 11.2 and 11.1 corresponds to N₁H and N₃H of barbituric acid, respectively, δ 8.4 a doublet of two protons, δ 7.1 a doublet for two protons

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Ar = 2-OHC₆H₄, 4-OCH₃C₆H₄, 4-ClC₆H₄, 2-ClC₆H₄, 2-OH-5-BrC₆H₄, 2-NO₂C₆H₄, 2-Furyl

Ar' = C₆H₄, 2,4-(OCH₃)₂C₆H₃, 2,5-(OCH₃)₂C₆H₃, 4-CH₃C₆H₄, 2-OHC₆H₄, 4-NO₂C₆H₄

Scheme 1

corresponds to aromatic protons, a singlet at δ 4.0 for three protons corresponds to OCH₃. Compound 2a was further confirmed by the mass spectral data. The mass spectrum of compound 2a shows a molecular ion peak at m/z 247 (M^+ , 100%). Formation of compound 2h was confirmed by the IR spectrum which shows the characteristic absorptions of NH at 3208, 3171 and C=O at 1743 cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR spectrum shows signals at δ 11.2 (1H, s, N₁H), 10.0 (1H, s, N₃H), 8.6–7.4 (11H, m, 10ArH and H-5 of pyrazole), 8.2 (1H, s, C=CH). Mass spec-

trum of compound 2h shows molecular ion peak at m/z 358 (M^+ , 100%). Further compounds 2a-c, 2g-j on chemoselective reduction with sodium borohydride in isopropyl alcohol as a proton donor solvent under stirring for 18 h furnishes the carbon-carbon double bond reduced compound 3a-c, 3g-j. The IR spectrum of compound 3a shows the characteristic absorptions of NH at 3254, 3146 and C=O at 1759 cm^{-1} and ¹H NMR spectrum of 3a shows a singlet for two protons at δ 10.6 corresponds to N₁H and N₃H of barbituric acid, δ 6.8 a

doublet for two protons, δ 6.5 a doublet for two protons corresponds to aromatic protons, a singlet at δ 3.5 for three protons corresponds to OCH_3 , a triplet at δ 3.4 corresponds to H-5 of barbituric acid and a doublet at δ 3.3 corresponds to methylene protons of benzyl group. Further confirmation of reduced products was established based on the mass spectral analysis, mass spectrum of compound 3a shows the molecular ion peak at m/z 249 (M^+ , 100%) gives the evidence for its molecular weight. The IR spectrum of compound 3h shows the characteristic absorptions of NH at 3347 and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ at 1734 cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR spectrum of compound 3h shows signals at δ 11.2 (1H, s, N_1H), 9.8 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.2–7.2 (11H, m, 10ArH, H-5 of pyrazole), 3.7 (1H, t, C_5H), 3.0 (2H, d, CH_2). Further formation of compound 3h was confirmed by the presence of molecular ion peak at m/z 360 (M^+ , 100%). However, compounds 2d-f and 2k-m failed to reduce the olefinic bond under identical conditions used for 2a-c and 2h-j to furnish the corresponding saturated compound. The physical data of synthesized compounds are tabulated in Table 1.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial activities were performed by cup

Table 1. Physical constants of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	Ar	Ar'	Yield ^a (%)	M.p. ^b (°C)
2a	4- $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	-	85	289–290
2b	2- OHC_6H_4	-	80	203–205
2c	4- ClC_6H_4	-	77	188–190
2d	2- ClC_6H_4	-	70	284–285
2e	5-Br, 2- OHC_6H_3	-	83	180–182
2f	2- $\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	-	48	215–220
2g	2-Furyl	-	80	232–235
2h	-	C_6H_5	85	255–260
2i	-	2- OHC_6H_4	55	245–250
2j	-	4- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	75	245–250
2k	-	4- $\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	65	262–268
2l	-	2,4-(OCH_3) $_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3$	80	270–275
2m	-	2,5-(OCH_3) $_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3$	65	280–285
3a	4- $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	-	85	193–195
3b	2- OHC_6H_4	-	71	280–284
3c	4- ClC_6H_4	-	70	208–212
3g	2-Furyl	-	71	158–161
3h	-	C_6H_5	55	275–280
3i	-	2,5-(OCH_3) $_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3$	65	258–265
3j	-	4- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	85	285–288

^aYield refers to purified product, ^bMelting points are uncorrected.

plate method. The sample was dissolved in DMF at the concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. Antibacterial activity screened against *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*. Antifungal activity was carried out against *A. niger* and *A. flavus* under aseptic conditions. Gentamycine and fluconazole were used as standard drug for antibacterial and antifungal activities respectively. The zone of inhibition was compared with standard drug after 24 h of incubation at 25 °C for antibacterial activity and 48 h at 30 °C for antifungal activity. Among the synthesized compounds 2j and 2l have shown good activity against bacteria *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*. Where as other compounds have shown moderate to poor activity against all the organisms. The compounds 2a-d, 2g, 3h and 3j exhibited good activity against fungal strains *A. niger* and *A. flavus*. All remaining synthesized compounds exhibited moderate to poor activity against all the organisms. Results were tabulated in Table 2.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded by using Thomas-Hoover melting point apparatus and were uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr disc were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Spectrum-one FTIR spectrophotometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) and ^1H NMR in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ and/or CDCl_3 on amx 400, 400 MHz spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shift in δ or ppm). Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102 Mass spectrometer using Argon/Xenon (6 kv, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel 'G' plates obtained from Whatman Inc, and a fluorescent indicator.

General procedure for the preparation of compounds (2a-m) :

A mixture of barbituric acid (1) (0.01 mol) and appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol) in methanol (50 ml) was refluxed on water bath for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and crystalline solid separated out was filtered and recrystallised from methanol to yield desired compounds 2a-m.

5-(4-Methoxybenzylidene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2a) : Yield : 85%. IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) : 3210, 3069, 1727, 1676 and 1179; ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$, δ in ppm) : 11.2 (1H, s, N_1H), 11.1 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.4 (2H, d, ArH), 8.2 (2H, d, ArH), 7.1 (1H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH_3). Mass (m/z) : 247 (M^+ , 100%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for : $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$: C, 58.54; H, 4.09; N, 11.38. Found : C, 58.50; H, 4.07; N, 11.32%.

Table 2. Antimicrobial activities of synthesized compounds

Compd.	Dose ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Antibacterial activity ^a (mm)			Antifungal activity ^a (mm)	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>
2a	1000	10	6	12	27	23
2b	1000	11	2	8	24	26
2c	1000	8	10	6	23	22
2d	1000	13	8	12	22	8
2e	1000	4	13	10	18	16
2f	1000	8	6	12	16	6
2g	1000	12	11	8	26	20
2h	1000	12	8	2	18	14
2i	1000	6	11	10	12	16
2j	1000	16	16	13	8	10
2k	1000	8	11	6	16	14
2l	1000	18	16	14	18	14
2m	1000	10	8	12	12	10
3a	1000	10	6	14	26	12
3b	1000	4	12	14	15	6
3c	1000	11	12	13	10	18
3g	1000	13	10	8	17	22
3h	1000	16	10	12	18	20
3i	1000	12	6	14	16	6
3j	1000	8	14	10	20	18
Control (DMF)	1000	0	0	0	0	0
Gentamycine	1000	20	20	24	-	-
Fluconazole	1000	-	-	-	25	24

^aZone of inhibition excluding well size 6 mm.

5-(2-Hydroxybenzylidene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2b): Yield : 80%. IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) : 3435, 3219, 3089, 1730, 1668; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 12.0 (1H, s, N_1H), 11.2 (1H, s, N_3H), 11.0 (1H, s, OH), 7.6–7.0 (4H, m, ArH), 7.4 (1H, s, C=CH). Mass (m/z) : 232 (M^+ , 100%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$: C, 56.90; H, 3.47; N, 12.06. Found : C, 56.82; H, 3.42; N, 12.02%.

5-(4-Chlorobenzylidene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2c) : Yield : 77%. IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) : 3214, 3151, 1756 and 809; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.1 (1H, s, N_1H), 11.0 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.3 (2H, d, ArH), 8.0 (2H, d, ArH), 7.3 (1H, s, C=CH). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$: C, 52.71; H, 2.82; Cl, 14.15; N, 11.18. Found : C, 52.70; H, 2.79; Cl, 14.13; N, 11.1

5-(2-Chlorobenzylidene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2d) : Yield : 50%. IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) : 3231, 3101, 1730 and 755; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.5 (1H, s, N_1H), 11.2 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.5 (1H, s, C=CH), 7.8–7.0 (4H, m, ArH). Mass (m/z) : 251 (M^+ , 15%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$: C, 52.71; H, 2.82; Cl, 14.15; N, 11.18. Found : C, 52.70; H, 2.79; Cl, 14.13; N, 11.16%.

5-(5-Bromo-2-hydroxybenzylidene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2e) : Yield : 83%. IR (KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) : 3322, 3101, 1743; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 12.1 (1H, s, N_1H), 11.2 (1H, s, N_3H), 11.0 (1H, s, OH), 8.4 (1H, s, C=CH), 7.4–6.9 (4H, m, ArH). Mass (m/z) : 310 (M^+ , 100%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_4$: C, 42.47; H, 2.27; Br, 25.69; N, 9.00. Found : C, 42.42;

H, 2.22; Br, 25.65; N, 8.98%.

5-(2-Nitrobenzylidene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2f) : Yield : 48%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3182, 1734; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.5 (1H, s, N_1H), 11.2 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.6 (1H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 8.2–7.5 (4H, m, ArH). Mass (m/z) : 260 (M^+ , 100%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$: C, 50.58; H, 2.70; N, 16.09. Found : C, 50.52; H, 2.69; N, 16.06%.

5-(Furan-2-ylidene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2g) : Yield : 80%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3324, 3147 and 1758; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.2 (1H, s, N_1H), 11.1 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.5 (1H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 8.0–6.8 (4H, m, ArH). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$: C, 49.49; H, 3.17; N, 14.43. Found : C, 49.48; H, 3.10; N, 14.40%.

5-((1,3-Diphenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methylene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2h) : Yield : 85%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3208, 3171, 1743; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.2 (1H, s, N_1H), 10.0 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.6–7.4 (11H, m, 10ArH, H-5 of pyrazole), 8.2 (1H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$). Mass (m/z) : 358 (M^+ , 100%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$: C, 67.03; H, 3.94; N, 15.63. Found : C, 67.02; H, 3.92; N, 15.62%.

5-((3-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methylene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2i) : Yield : 55%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3473, 3182, 3130, 1705; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.2 (1H, s, N_1H), 10.4 (1H, s, N_3H), 10.0 (1H, s, OH), 8.6 (1H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 7.8–6.8 (10H, m, 9ArH, H-5 of pyrazole). Mass (m/z) : 374 (M^+ , 10%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$: C, 64.17; H, 3.77; N, 14.97. Found : C, 64.18; H, 3.75; N, 14.96%.

5-((3-p-Tolyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methylene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2j) : Yield : 75%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3179, 1731; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.4 (1H, s, N_1H), 9.8 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.2 (1H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 7.9–7.4 (10H, m, 9ArH, H-5 of pyrazole), 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3). Mass (m/z) : 372 (M^+ , 50%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$: C, 67.73; H, 4.33; N, 15.05. Found : C, 67.72; H, 4.31; N, 15.04%.

5-((3-(4-Nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methylene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2k) : Yield : 65%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3206, 3172, 1743; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.2 (1H, s, N_1H), 9.8 (1H, s,

N_3H), 8.5 (1H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 7.8–6.4 (10H, m, 9ArH, H-5 of pyrazole). Mass (m/z) : 403 (M^+ , 5%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{O}_5$: C, 59.56; H, 3.25; N, 17.36. Found : C, 59.55; H, 3.24; N, 17.34%.

5-((3-(2,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methylene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2l) : Yield : 80%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3189, 1737; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.2 (1H, s, N_1H), 9.8 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.5 (1H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 8.2–7.0 (9H, m, 8ArH, H-5 of pyrazole), 3.7 (6H, s, OCH_3). Mass (m/z) : 418 (M^+ , 30%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5$: C, 63.15; H, 4.34; N, 13.39. Found : C, 63.12; H, 4.31; N, 13.38%.

5-((3-(2,5-Dimethoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methylene)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (2m) : Yield : 65%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3211 (NH), 1729 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.4 (1H, s, N_1H), 9.8 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.3 (1H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 8.0–7.0 (9H, m, 8ArH, H-5 of pyrazole), 3.7 (6H, s, OCH_3). Mass (m/z) : 418 (M^+ , 100%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5$: C, 63.15; H, 4.34; N, 13.39. Found : C, 63.14; H, 4.33; N, 13.37%.

General procedure for the preparation of compounds (3a-c, 3g-j) :

A mixture of chalcone **2a-c**, **2g-j** (0.01 mol) in 50 ml of isopropyl alcohol and sodium borohydride were added portion wise (0.05 mol) and the mixture was stirred for 18 h. Excess sodium borohydride was destroyed by gradual addition of 1 N HCl. Solid separated was filtrated, washed repeatedly with water and recrystallised from methanol to get desired compounds **3a-c**, **3g-j**.

5-(4-Methoxybenzyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (3a) : Yield : 97%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3254, 3146, 1759; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 10.6 (2H, s, N_1H and N_3H), 6.8 (2H, d, ArH), 6.5 (2H, d, ArH), 3.5 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.4 (1H, t, C_5H), 3.3 (2H, d, CH_2Ph). Mass (m/z) : 249 (M^+ , 100%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$: C, 58.06; H, 4.87; N, 11.29. Found : C, 58.03; H, 4.81; N, 11.25%.

5-(2-Hydroxybenzyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (3b) : Yield : 71%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3278, 3118, 1710; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 10.7 (2H, s, N_1H and N_3H), 7.6 (1H, s, OH), 7.1–6.9 (4H, d, ArH), 2.5 (1H, t, C_5H), 2.0 (2H, d, CH_2). Mass (m/z) : 235 (M^+ , 100%).

Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{10}N_2O_4$: C, 56.41; H, 4.30; N, 11.96. Found : C, 56.39; H, 4.25; N, 11.88%.

5-(4-Chlorobenzyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (3c) : Yield : 70%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3265, 3149, 1764, 753; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 10.7 (2H, s, N_1H and N_3H), 7.2–6.9 (4H, m, ArH), 3.4 (1H, t, C_5H), 3.2 (2H, d, CH_2). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $C_{11}H_9ClN_2O_3$: C, 52.29; H, 3.59; Cl, 14.03; N, 11.09. Found : C, 52.25; H, 3.52; Cl, 14.02; N, 11.06%.

5-((Furan-2-yl)methyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (3g) : Yield : 71%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3251, 3123, 1712; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 10.7 (2H, s, N_1H and N_3H), 7.2–5.8 (3H, m, ArH), 3.4 (1H, t, C_5H), 3.2 (2H, d, CH_2). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $C_8H_8N_2O_4$: C, 51.93; H, 3.87; N, 13.46. Found : C, 51.92; H, 3.84; N, 13.45%.

5-((1,3-Diphenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (3h) : Yield : 85%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3347, 1734; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 11.2 (1H, s, N_1H), 9.8 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.2–7.2 (11H, m, 10ArH, H-5 of pyrazole), 3.7 (1H, t, C_5H), 3.0 (2H, d, CH_2). Mass (m/z) : 360 (M^+ , 100%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_3$: C, 66.66; H, 4.48; N, 15.55. Found : C, 66.65; H, 4.47; N, 15.53%.

5-((3-(2,5-Dimethoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (3i) : Yield : 55%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3355, 1736; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 10.2 (1H, s, N_1H), 9.8 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.2–6.5 (9H, m, 8ArH, H-5 of pyrazole), 3.6 (6H, s, OCH_3), 3.2 (1H, t, C_5H), 2.7 (2H, d, CH_2). Mass (m/z) : 420 (M^+ , 100%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{20}N_4O_5$: C, 62.85; H, 4.79; N, 13.33. Found : C, 62.84; H, 4.77; N, 13.32%.

5-((1-Phenyl-3-p-tolyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methyl)pyrimidin-2,4,6-trione (3j) : Yield : 65%. IR (KBr, ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) : 3354, 1748; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ in ppm) : 10.2 (1H, s, N_1H), 9.8 (1H, s, N_3H), 8.0–7.2 (10H, m, 9ArH, H-5 of pyrazole), 3.0 (1H, t, C_5H), 2.6 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.4 (2H, d, CH_2). Mass (m/z) : 374 (M^+ , 100%). Elemental analysis : Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{18}N_4O_3$: C, 67.37; H, 4.85; N, 14.96. Found : C, 67.36; H, 4.83; N, 14.95%.

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